

Deliverable D2.4 2nd Report on delivered data management and stewardship courses

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Log of changes

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the delivered data management (DM) and data stewardship (DS) training events across ELIXIR Nodes in the period from January 1, 2022 to June 30, 2023 as well as cumulative report of DM and DS training events from the start of the project until June 30, 2023. In the observed period from January 1, 2022 until June 30, 2023 there were 73 additional DM training events: 51 events in 2022 and 22 events in 2023, organised by 15 Nodes, with 1713 participants. The most covered training gap was DM Plans (33 training events), followed by Reproducibility (25 training events) and FAIR (21 training events). Cumulatively there were 149 courses organised by 18 Nodes with more than 4500 participants.

The organisation of training events was carried out in collaboration with three other WP2 Tasks: Identification of training needs (T2.1), Developing materials (T2.2) and Outreach (T2.4). The training events encompass both reruns of existing courses (including updated courses), as well as the delivery of new courses based on the new training materials developed in Task 2.2. The report is based on the continuously updated ELIXIR-CONVERGE roadmap for DM training and capacity building, which was initially provided in D2.1.

A summary of key data on the training events in the observed periods covered by this Deliverable is presented in the Results section. The collected data show how the delivery of training events improved from the start of ELIXIR-CONVERGE to better match training gaps and needs in the ELIXIR community and wider in the European research area.

The data and metadata about training events were collected in the Training Inventory spreadsheet¹, including the information on training gaps covered by each event. The Training Inventory spreadsheet proved as a useful tool for collecting information and will continue to serve as an useful resource for training data collection beyond the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project until the more user friendly and system solution will be prepared as a part of ELIXIR Training Lifecycle. The collected information was

¹ [WP2 Training Inventory](#), data about training events were collected until July 24, 2023

helpful for shaping and will help to improve RDM Trainer Network (former Community of Practice of DM/DS trainers) activities as planned in the ELIXIR Training Platform 2024-2028 Programme. The RDM Trainer Network also includes national Nodes in order to accelerate the alignment of ELIXIR training efforts with national activities and to ensure sustainability of training.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	No
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	Yes
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	Yes
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	Yes

Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	Yes
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No

3. Introduction

The objective of CONVERGE WP2 was to build a sustainable programme of training and capacity building in Data Management (DM). This is in line with Objective 2 (Strengthen Europe’s DM capacity through a comprehensive training programme) of ELIXIR-CONVERGE. The main target audiences for training and capacity building events that were overlooked by WP2 were researchers, data managers and data stewards across all ELIXIR Nodes.

The main scope of this deliverable is to report on training events delivered by ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 partners in the period from January 1, 2022 to June 30, 2023. These training events form part of the ELIXIR Training and Capacity Building Programme in DM, which provides key data management training to researchers and data support professionals (o.a. data managers and data stewards) in the European Research Area. To harmonise ongoing training efforts, the training events developed in WP2 use tools developed by ELIXIR Training Platform (TrP), e.g. the ELIXIR Training Toolkit, the ELIXIR Training Metrics Database (TMD), the Quality & Impact strategy, and TeSS. Furthermore, with the help of ELIXIR TrP the aim beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE is to FAIRify all training materials developed in WP2.

The ELIXIR Training and Capacity Building Programme in DM covers the following types of training events:

- Training courses or workshops with hands-on activities
- Hackathons where participants collaborate to improve the DM tools and practice, and create new training materials
- Training events for new trainers in DM and data stewardship (DS)

ELIXIR-CONVERGE uses international standards to connect the distributed local support for DM across Europe. The main resources are the people - life science DM professionals (WP1), the shared toolkit (WP3) with a.o. data from Demonstrator Projects (WP5), and the skills that can be learned (WP2). WP2 has set up the DM Training Programme which is boosting education and awareness about DM skills. This programme supports other WPs creating training activities that will and did enhance the outcomes of their activities. The collaborations with other WPs extend beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE to ensure sustainability after the end of the project.

- WP1: Trainers/teachers were identified among DM experts.
- WP3: RDMkit related training activities, e.g. participation in WP3 contentathons to define the data steward roles in the RDMkit.
- WP4: Dissemination of training materials.
- WP5: Training needs related to the Demonstrator Projects were identified and a training inventory was set up.
- WP6: Definition of the ELIXIR Node Coordinators Curriculum, now further developed in the ELITMa project (funded as WP2 uplift project).
- WP7: Training materials and activities on how to set up your local EGA and join the federated EGA that will continue beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE as a part of Human Data communities activities in collaboration with ELIXIR TrP
- WP9: Management of COVID-19 / SARS-CoV-2 data, tools and services.

The information on delivered courses has been collected in the ELIXIR CONVERGE WP2 Training Inventory and Roadmap and the data presented in this deliverable have been extracted from the training inventory. An emphasis was put on the TeSS registration of training events, availability of open-access training materials related to these events (to comply with the FAIR principle), as well as on training gaps addressed by the delivered events.

4. Description of work accomplished

Participating Nodes delivered DM/DS training events based on the training needs identified in Task 2.1 and in collaboration with Task 2.2 that was helping in development of the new training materials. Data on the delivered training events were collected in the Training Inventory spreadsheet within the Training Events tab². The metadata collected in this tab included (among others) the event title, target audience, start date and duration, number of participants, training materials URL, as well as the TeSS registration URL (if it exists). The collected metadata about events included also the information about the addressed training gaps and the order of priority for these gaps.

Hackathons to generate training materials that cover the prioritised training gaps were organised by T2.2 and the results have been described in [D2.2](#)³. These hackathons resulted in the development of new training materials that were already used for some of the delivered training events. Other ELIXIR-CONVERGE WPs also collaborated in training activities. Collaboration with WP3 was focused on the creation of training materials and events for the ELIXIR DM Toolkit, our work with WP5 was focused on the training on Demonstrator Projects, while we also supported training efforts of the new COVID-19 and FEQA related WPs (WP7 to WP9).

4.1 Categories of training events

Delivered training events can be sorted in four main categories:

- Training courses with hands-on activities
- Webinars
- Hackathons
- Train-the-Trainer (TtT) events

Training courses with hands-on activities represent the most numerous category of training events. These events are sometimes called workshops, summer schools etc. During the Covid-19 pandemic courses were mostly online but they have since mostly returned to the face-to-face format. Webinars are online lectures which allow participants to interact with teachers (ask questions etc.). Demo presentations are also often part of webinars. Hackathons are specialised meetings of experts to brainstorm and produce new training materials, write code, prepare guidelines and plans of action. These events are also known as contentathons. Train-the-Trainer (TtT) events are courses for people who would like to become (better) trainers involved in the ELIXIR DM Training and Capacity Building Programme. Most TtT participants have previous involvement with ELIXIR but lack formal training in teaching skills. TtT events are the key component of the capacity building dimension of the programme, and the outcome of TtT is an increased number of skilled trainers who will continue to carry out the training activities beyond the end of ELIXIR-CONVERGE. All these training events did contribute to the better awareness and capacity building in the area of DM/DS for the whole ELIXIR network as well as for the involved Nodes.

5. Results

The Deliverable D2.4 covers the period from January 1, 2022 to June 30, 2023 with the data about

² [WP2 Training Inventory](#)

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/8168922>

training events collected until July 24, 2023. In this period there were 73 training events: 51 events in 2022 and 22 events in 2023, organised by 15 Nodes, with 1713 participants. 43/73 courses have open-access training materials, while 44/73 new training events are registered in [TeSS](#)⁴. The training events for the observed period are listed in Table 1 below, as well as in the [ELIXIR CONVERGE WP2 Training Inventory and Roadmap](#)⁵ (observed on July 24, 2023). Since the start of CONVERGE in February 2020 there were 149 training events in total, organised by 18 Nodes, with 4522 participants. Total numbers are presented in Figure 1 and Tables 1 to 3.

Figure 1: Summary of the training events delivered from February 2020 until June 2023.

18 additional training events related to the CONVERGE WP5 demonstrator projects (10 Nodes, 150+ participants) are listed in the ELIXIR [CONVERGE WP5 Training Inventory](#)⁶. 14 of those 18 events have open-access training materials.

Table 1: List of delivered training events between January 1, 2022 and June 30, 2023 (source WP2 Training Inventory and Roadmap⁵ observed on July 24, 2023).

No.	Year	Training event (short name)	Node	Participants	TeSS	Materials	Main priority training gap addressed
1	2022	DMP tools	ES	60	yes	yes	DMPs
2	2022	Containers and workflow pipelines	BE	34	no	yes	Reproducibility

⁴<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

⁵<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Vu-qzbJZOOhKSJeUhzF4NDIUSDzZY7FPO8y2zDs-oDP4/edit?usp=sharing>

⁶https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1az4U22K4pPOnzbn_JcQy4bSMRaBKMGA0eHM2t07ZHeU/edit?usp=sharing

3	2022	Introduction to HPC	SI	20	yes	no	Processing
4	2022	RDM & DMP 1	CH	25	yes	no	DMPs
5	2022	The FAIR principles 1	EE	17	yes	yes	FAIR
6	2022	RDM course	FI	98	yes	yes	DMPs
7	2022	The FAIR principles 2	EE	23	yes	yes	FAIR
8	2022	Programming skills for biocuration	EMBL	124	no	yes	Specialised formation
9	2022	DM of research data (in Catalan)	ES	30	no	no	DMPs
10	2022	Text mining for biocuration	EMBL	58	no	yes	Capturing data
11	2022	Ontologies for biocuration	EMBL	51	no	yes	Documentation
12	2022	How to make your messy data usable 1	EE	17	yes	yes	Processing
13	2022	Working with sensitive data	EMBL	44	no	yes	Publishing
14	2022	Introduction to DM practices 1	SE	25	yes	yes	DMPs
15	2022	Metadata and README 1	EE	22	yes	yes	Metadata
16	2022	Biocuration in industry	EMBL	51	no	yes	DM/DS
17	2022	Q-EBRA workshop	ES	22	yes	yes	DMPs
18	2022	Bring your own DMP - Lecture	EE	26	yes	no	DMPs
19	2022	Bring your own DMP 1	EE	5	yes	no	DMPs
20	2022	Bring your own DMP 2	EE	8	yes	no	DMPs
21	2022	RDM for life scientists 1	NO	20	yes	yes	DMPs
22	2022	Introduction to Git & GitHub 1	BE	11	no	yes	Reproducibility
23	2022	RDM & DMP 2	CH	12	no	no	DMPs
24	2022	Metadata and README 2	EE	6	yes	yes	Metadata
25	2022	Introduction to Git & GitHub 2	BE	15	no	yes	Reproducibility
26	2022	RDM for life scientists 2	NO	20	yes	yes	/
27	2022	Licensing research outputs 1	EE	4	yes	yes	Publishing

28	2022	How to make your messy data usable 2	EE	11	yes	yes	Processing
29	2022	Introduction to DM practices 2	SE	25	yes	yes	DMPs
30	2022	Docker and Singularity for data analysis	BE	16	no	yes	Reproducibility
31	2022	Data visualisation 1	EE	13	yes	yes	Publishing
32	2022	RDM & DMP 3	CH	20	yes	no	DMPs
33	2022	How to make your messy data usable 3	EE	3	yes	yes	Processing
34	2022	DM of research data (in Spanish)	ES	31	no	no	DMPs
35	2022	Nextflow for data analysis	BE	16	no	yes	Reproducibility
36	2022	NeLS hands-on workshop	NO	40	no	yes	Infrastructure
37	2022	Taller DM tips	ES	33	yes	yes	DMPs
38	2022	FAIR principles applied to bioinformatics	FR	15	yes	no	Reproducibility
39	2022	Create a DMP with DSW	NO	3	yes	no	/
40	2022	Reproducible research in R 1	UK	14	yes	no	Reproducibility
41	2022	Reproducible research in R 2	UK	48	yes	no	Reproducibility
42	2022	Reproducible research in R 3	UK	37	yes	no	Reproducibility
43	2022	DSW and DMP Introduction for VUT	CZ	40	no	no	DMPs
44	2022	FAIR in (biological) practice	DE	10	no	no	FAIR
45	2022	Boost your DMP	DE	13	no	no	DMPs
46	2022	Boost your DMP	DE	9	no	no	DMPs
47	2022	Keep your Project on Track!	DE	11	no	no	Reproducibility
48	2022	Let's make a Plan! Using DMPTool to outline our RDM	DE	17	no	no	DMPs
49	2022	Let's make a Plan! Using DMPTool to outline our RDM	DE	12	no	no	DMPs

50	2022	Let's make a Plan! Using DMPTool to outline our RDM	DE	14	no	no	DMPs
51	2023	Training data stewards for life sciences	PT	24	yes	yes	DM/DS
52	2023	Create and Handle DMPs with DSW	NO	15	yes	no	/
53	2023	RDM & DMP 4	CH	30	yes	no	DMPs
54	2023	Day2Day Data Management 1	PT	28	yes	yes	ELIXIR DMKit
55	2023	Day2Day Data Management 2	PT	25	yes	yes	ELIXIR DMKit
56	2023	Day2Day Data Management 3	PT	29	yes	yes	ELIXIR DMKit
57	2023	Day2Day Data Management 4	PT	18	yes	yes	ELIXIR DMKit
58	2023	Introduction to DMPs	PT	16	yes	yes	DMPs
59	2023	FAIR in a nutshell	EE	9	yes	yes	FAIR
60	2023	Open Science and DMP in Estonia	EE	6	yes	yes	DMPs
61	2023	Bring your own DMP 3	EE	16	yes	yes	DMPs
62	2023	Bring your own DMP 4	EE	7	yes	yes	DMPs
63	2023	Repositories and HPCs in Estonia	EE	23	yes	yes	Infrastructure
64	2023	Metadata and README 3	EE	15	yes	yes	Metadata
65	2023	Licensing research outputs 2	EE	3	yes	yes	Publishing
66	2023	Introduction to RDM	LU	12	no	no	/
67	2023	FAIR RDM & DMP	CH	14	yes	no	DMPs
68	2023	DSW and DMP Introduction for BIOCEV (IBT)	CZ	20	no	no	DMPs
69	2023	Health-RI course: FAIR DS basics	NL	20	no	yes	DM/DS
70	2023	ELITMa: Module 2 "DM Strategy"	NL	35	no	yes	Policies
71	2023	de.NBI Spring School - DM	DE	23	no	no	DMPs
72	2023	DMP Hackathon 2022	DE	20	no	no	DMPs
73	2023	DMP Hackathon 2023	DE	6	no	no	DMPs

For every delivered training event the course organisers were asked to provide also information about which training gaps were addressed with the observed course. The collected priority training gaps addressed by the delivered training events in the period January 2022 - June 2023 are listed in Table 2. Some of the training gaps were often prioritised by event organisers, e.g. DM Plans and Reproducibility, while other gaps were put forward less often. Even though not a lot of training events were foreseen for the ELIXIR RDMkit (originally mentioned as ELIXIR DM Toolkit), there were 4 courses on the ELIXIR RDMkit in the main period covered by this deliverable (January 2022 - June 2023), which is more than in the preceding period (February 2020 - December 2021). This is a sign that the RDMkit is gaining ground in the European research community. The table also shows the total number of training events delivered during ELIXIR-CONVERGE that cover a particular training gap.

Table 2: Number of delivered training events per main priority training gap addressed by the event

Main priority training gap	Training events 02/2020 - 31/12/2021	Training events 01/01/2022 - 30/06/2023	Training events total
DMPs	37	31	68
Reproducibility	5	10	15
Data management & data stewardship	11	4	15
FAIR	13	4	17
Processing and analysing	4	4	8
ELIXIR RDMkit	2	4	6
Publishing, sharing and archiving data	3	4	7
Metadata	/	3	3
Infrastructure for storing and sharing data	/	2	2
Capturing data / collecting data yourself	/	1	1
Documentation & organising data	/	1	1
Specialised formation	/	1	1

Finding data	1	/	1
Not available	/	4	4
Total	76	73	149

The training events delivered in the period January 2022 - June 2023 (that were registered and verified in the training inventory) were organised by 15 ELIXIR Nodes, which are listed in Table 3. Only verified events from the training inventory are included. The table also shows the number of training events in the preceding period (February 2020 - December 31, 2021), as well as the total number of training events organised per Node during ELIXIR-CONVERGE.

Table 3: Number of delivered training events per Node

Node	Training events 02/2020 - 31/12/2021	Training events 01/01/2022 - 30/06/2023	Training events total
Estonia	3	19	22
Germany	3	10	13
Portugal	8	6	14
Spain	6	5	11
EMBL-EBI	6	5	11
Switzerland	3	5	8
Belgium	2	5	7
Norway	2	5	7
United Kingdom	/	3	3
Czech Republic	20	2	22
Netherlands	4	2	6
Sweden	3	2	5
Finland	7	1	8
France	5	1	6
Luxembourg	1	1	2
Slovenia	1	1	2

Israel	1	/	1
Italy	1	/	1
Total	76	73	149

6. Conclusions

Between January 1, 2022 and June 30, 2023 the partners of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project reported to WP2 (Training and Capacity Building) on 73 delivered DM/DS training events organised by 15 countries/ELIXIR Nodes with 1713 participants. Cumulatively there were 149 training events by the end of 2021 until June 30, 2023 with a total 4522 participants. This is already a remarkable outcome. Various metadata about delivered DM/DS training events were collected. For every training event the topics covered by the event were matched with the identified training gaps. With more and more delivered training events, the matching with the main identified training gap helps us to better understand the difference between the identified gaps and the topics of actual events. Better matching with all identified training gaps will enable us to optimise the alignment of the training roadmap with the training needs also beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE.

This Deliverable summarises information about delivered DM/DS training events. DM Plans topic was the topic around which the training events were most frequently organised by the Nodes, they were followed by FAIR, DM/DS and Reproducibility that were almost equally represented, next group of topics were data processing, data publishing and ELIXIR RDMkit. The metadata on training gaps in the training inventory spreadsheet provide the understanding of how actual training events cover previously identified training gaps. We have used this information on main training gaps to better align the training roadmap with actual training needs expressed by the Nodes.

New materials and courses will continue to boost the capacity building efforts not only for the well-covered training topics but also for the topics with a smaller number of delivered training events well beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE. Training delivery is especially important for the other activities of ELIXIR network connected to DM/DS and training, e.g. ELIXIR DM Toolkit and TMD.

7. Impact

The collected data from the Training Inventory did serve and will continue to serve as guidelines to improve the delivery of training events. We will focus our efforts on the training gaps that were considered important by a variety of Nodes (e.g. DM plans and FAIR, followed by Data publishing and reproducibility) also beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE.

The impact from the ELIXIR-CONVERGE training programme is evident both at the Node level and within the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project where different work packages collaborated to align their training activities. New training materials have been developed that will be used for new courses beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE while DM/DS training events will continue to be delivered in the final period of the project as well as beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE. The number of training events participants steadily increased throughout the project. The metrics data from the DM/DS training events are included in the Training Metrics Database (TMD).

The following indicators were measured to assess the impact of the Training and Capacity Building programme:

- Number of DM training events organised
- Countries where training is organised and number of training events per country
- Number of participants receiving training
- Feedback from training participants (short-term feedback - STF; long-term feedback - LTF may be added)
- Number of trainers trained via the DM Train-the-Trainer (TtT) programme

Two new target indicators were included at the completion of hackathon development by T2.2:

- Number of training events based on training materials developed by T2.2 hackathons.
- Number of gaps covered by delivered training events

The pinnacle of the WP2 training activities has been the rollout of the RDM Training Network that enables adoption of the best DM practices among research communities. The RDM Training Network as a part of ELIXIR RDM Community and in collaboration with ELIXIR TrP will continue to support training in the DM/DS area beyond the end of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. DM training experts from CONVERGE WP1, WP3, WP5, WP7 and WP9 are included in the ELIXIR RDM Community (which emerged from WP1) and already participate in training activities, while DM/DS training events organised that were organised by WP2 will be taken over by ELIXIR TrP and will continue to consider special interests of ELIXIR Nodes and Communities. The Capacity Building activities included the organisation of the Train-the-Trainer courses related to DM/DS that helped to improve the training skills of DM/DS trainers.

8. Next Steps

DM/DS training events were organised by the nodes participating in T2.3. Some of the organised and observed training events already used the new DM/DS training materials that were developed via hackathons organised in T2.2. Within T2.3 the analysis of the training gaps addressed by training events was done. Metadata was collected by the Training Inventory. We will continue with the collection and analysis of metadata on DM/DS training events beyond the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. We foresee that the metadata could be sustainably collected by TeSS or by the newly developed Training Metrics Database (TMD). TMD could provide a standard training gaps visualisation that will show the frequency and priority of each gap. A “CONVERGE” tag has already been added to the TMD. This will improve the annotation of training events in the TMD that were related to the CONVERGE project.

Finally, work is underway to establish the RDM Trainer Network (of DM/DS trainers), from both WP2 and national Nodes. This will contribute significantly to the synchronisation of DM/DS training efforts with national activities. It will also be a good step towards producing sustainable training materials. The RDM Trainer Network will become an integral part of the newly started ELIXIR RDM Community.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

This deliverable was originally due on May 31, 2023. A delay was requested as previous deliverables that this one depended on were also delayed. As a consequence, training events carried out until the end of June 2023 are now also included in the scope of this deliverable. The delay will not affect the overall target of the project.

